

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ACCOUNT FOR THE INFLUENCE OF THE ECCENTRICITY OF CYLINDRICAL INSTALLATIONS FOR MEASURING THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF SUBSTANCES

Naziyev J.

doctor of technical sciences, professor of «Physics» department of Azerbaijan State University of Oil and Industry (Baku, Azerbaijan)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7032332>

Abstract

In cylindrical measuring devices for determining thermal conductivity, the heat flow and the temperature difference between coaxial endless cylindrical surfaces are considered. The technique for calculating the thermal conductivity for this case has long been worked out. In this work, the influence of the eccentricity of the working cylindrical surfaces of devices is theoretically determined when calculating the thermal conductivity. Approximate equations are found for calculating the thermal conductivity of liquids and gases.

Keywords: heat transfer, thermal conductivity, cylindrical calorimeter, eccentricity

When designing new technological processes, the correct selection of materials for the manufacture of equipment is necessary. These devices should be as hardy as possible, and the processes should be efficient. Data on the thermal conductivity of substances are needed to calculate the heat transfer processes taking place in these devices.

There are many experimental methods for determining thermal conductivities, both stationary and non-stationary [1, p. 19-72]. Non-stationary methods have a number of advantages and therefore are more often used [2, p. 347-355; 3, p. 12-22]. Depending on the shapes of the working surfaces, cylindrical, spherical and flat bicalorimeters are distinguished [1, p. 77-81].

For accurate calculations of thermal conductivity by these methods, it is necessary to take into account many errors in the eccentricity of the measuring cylinders. Eccentricity greatly affects the result of calculations.

Let us determine the exact solution of the problem of the influence of eccentricity for eccentric cylinders. Let's consider the differential heat equation [4, p. 30]

$$\frac{\partial^2 t}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 t}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

When solving equation (1), we use the method of sources (superposition principle), in which the temperature field is found by adding the temperature fields created by individual heat sources.

Two symmetrically located sources A and B excite a joint temperature field (Fig.1). For the case of infinite cylinders, the temperature difference is determined by the following expression:

$$\theta = \frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln \frac{r''}{r'} \quad (2)$$

For a point m on the first cylindrical surface, we can write:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{r_m''}{r_m'} &= \frac{r_m'' + d}{d - r_m'} \\ r_m'' - r_m' &= 2(h - r) \\ r_m'' + r_m' &= 2Y_0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Solving the system of equations (3), we find

$$h = \frac{r^2 + (a')^2}{2a'} \quad (4)$$

Given that $y_0 = h - a'$.

For the second cylindrical surface with radius R:

$$H = \frac{R^2 + (a'')^2}{2a''} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1

Also for both surfaces we can write:

$$\frac{r_m''}{r_m'} = -\frac{r}{a'} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{r_M''}{r_M'} = -\frac{R}{a''} \quad (7)$$

Temperature difference between eccentric cylindrical surfaces

$$\Delta t = \frac{1}{2\pi\lambda} Q_t \ln \frac{ra''}{Ra'} \quad (8)$$

We use the last expression and express a' and a'' in terms of the eccentricity a

$$\lambda = \frac{Q_t}{2\pi\Delta t} \ln \frac{r \left[R^2 - r^2 + a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 - a^2)^2 - 4a^2 r^2} \right]}{R \left[R^2 - r^2 - a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 - a^2)^2 - 4a^2 r^2} \right]} \quad (12)$$

From (9), (4) and (5) we find the second solution for a' and a''

$$a' = \frac{R^2 - r^2 - a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 + a^2)^2 - 4a^2 R^2}}{2a} \quad (13)$$

$$a'' = \frac{R^2 - r^2 + a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 + a^2)^2 - 4a^2 R^2}}{2a} \quad (14)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a'' - a' &= a \\ H - h &= a \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Using expressions (9), as well as (4) and (5), we find

$$a' = \frac{R^2 - r^2 - a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 - a^2)^2 - 4a^2 r^2}}{2a} \quad (10)$$

$$a'' = \frac{R^2 - r^2 + a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 - a^2)^2 - 4a^2 r^2}}{2a} \quad (11)$$

From (8), (10) and (11) we get

as well as

$$\lambda = \frac{Q_l}{2\pi\Delta t} \ln \frac{r \left[R^2 - r^2 + a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 + a^2)^2 - 4a^2 R^2} \right]}{R \left[R^2 - r^2 - a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 + a^2)^2 - 4a^2 R^2} \right]}. \quad (15)$$

From (12) at $a = 0$, for the case of coaxial cylinders we have

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \frac{r \left[R^2 - r^2 + a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 - a^2)^2 - 4a^2 r^2} \right]}{R \left[R^2 - r^2 - a^2 - \sqrt{(R^2 - r^2 - a^2)^2 - 4a^2 r^2} \right]} = \frac{R}{r}. \quad (16)$$

Then, under certain assumptions, we can obtain an approximate formula

$$\lambda = \frac{Q_l}{2\pi\Delta t} \ln \frac{r \left[R + r + a - \sqrt{(R + r - a)^2 - 4 \frac{ar^2}{R - r}} \right]}{R \left[R + r - a - \sqrt{(R + r - a)^2 - 4 \frac{ar^2}{R - r}} \right]}. \quad (17)$$

The last equation for the values $d_1 = 0,1mm$, $d_2 = 1,5mm$, $a = 0,1mm$ gives the error 0.5%, and equation (12) 0.02%.

References:

1. Назиев Д.Я. Теплопроводность углеводородов и методы ее измерения. Монография. Баку, Азербайджан. 2001. - 357 с.
2. Platonov E.S. Instruments for measuring thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity, and specific heat under monotonic heating. Compendium of thermo-physical properties measurement methods. Vol. 2. Recommended measurement techniques and practices. Plenum Press New York and London. 1992. - 643 p.

3. Litovsky E., Issoufov V., Horodetsky S., Kleiman J. Express methods for determination of thermo-physical properties of different types of materials within a temperature range of -150°C to $+1800^{\circ}\text{C}$. Proceedings of 31-th Int. Thermal conductivity conference and 19-th Thermal Expansion Symposium. Canada. 2011. - 325p.
4. Цветков Ф. Ф., Григорьев Б. А. Тепломассообмен : учебник для вузов. М. : Издательский дом МЭИ, 2011. - 562 с.